

A comparative life cycle assessment of disposal and recycling pathways for spent lithium-ion battery electrolyte

Zbyněk Plachý , Michael Fridrich & Anna Pražanová

To cite this article: Zbyněk Plachý , Michael Fridrich & Anna Pražanová (2026) A comparative life cycle assessment of disposal and recycling pathways for spent lithium-ion battery electrolyte, Green Chemistry Letters and Reviews, 19:1, 2640679, DOI: [10.1080/17518253.2026.2640679](https://doi.org/10.1080/17518253.2026.2640679)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/17518253.2026.2640679>

© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group

[View supplementary material](#)

Published online: 04 Mar 2026.

[Submit your article to this journal](#)

[View related articles](#)

[View Crossmark data](#)

A comparative life cycle assessment of disposal and recycling pathways for spent lithium-ion battery electrolyte

Zbyněk Plachý^a, Michael Fridrich^{a,b} and Anna Pražanová^a

^aDepartment of Electrotechnology, Czech Technical University in Prague, Prague, Czech Republic; ^bEnvironment Centre, Charles University, Prague, Czech Republic

ABSTRACT

While lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) are crucial for global decarbonization, the management of their hazardous organic electrolyte represents a critical yet frequently overlooked bottleneck in the circular economy. Containing lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF₆) salt dissolved in flammable carbonates, the electrolyte poses severe safety risks through thermal instability and toxic hydrogen fluoride emissions, while its energy-intensive synthesis makes its destruction a significant resource loss. This study addresses this gap by providing a rigorous 'gate-to-gate' life cycle assessment (LCA) of four end-of-life (EOL) pathways: direct disposal (incineration, chemical neutralization) and recycling (vacuum pyrolysis, distillation extraction). Modeled in SimaPro using the Ecoinvent 3.9 database, the analysis of a 100-litre functional unit of LiPF₆ electrolyte reveals a definitive environmental performance hierarchy driven by the quality and functionality of recovered materials. Distillation extraction, enabling a high-purity closed-loop, was uniquely identified as providing a net environmental benefit with a climate change credit of – 2.46 kg CO₂ eq. Conversely, incineration emerged as the most detrimental option (+11.29 kg CO₂ eq.) due to extreme energy demands and hazardous residue generation. The findings empirically demonstrate that non-destructive chemical recovery is fundamentally superior to energy-oriented downcycling, providing a quantitative framework to prioritize high-value circularity in future battery regulations and industrial investments.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 25 September 2025
Accepted 28 February 2026

KEYWORDS

Lithium-ion battery; life cycle assessment; end-of-life; electrolyte pre-treatment

1. Introduction

The global transition towards a decarbonized energy and transportation infrastructure fundamentally depends on the widespread adoption of high-performance energy storage technologies (1–3). Among these, lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) have emerged as the cornerstone technology, enabling the proliferation of electric vehicles, grid-scale stationary storage systems, and portable electronics (4–7). This technological ascendancy represents a critical success in the collective effort to mitigate climate change by displacing fossil

CONTACT Zbyněk Plachý Department of Electrotechnology, Czech Technical University in Prague, Technická 2, Prague 160 00, Czech Republic

 Supplemental data for this article can be accessed online at <https://doi.org/10.1080/17518253.2026.2640679>.

© 2026 The Author(s). Published by Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group
This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited. The terms on which this article has been published allow the posting of the Accepted Manuscript in a repository by the author(s) or with their consent.

fuel dependence. However, this rapid and exponential growth in LIB production precipitates an equally unprecedented challenge: a forthcoming wave of end-of-life (EOL) batteries, the scale of which will test the limits of existing waste management infrastructure and resource supply chains (8–10).

The effective management of this impending deluge of spent LIBs is crucial, not only to prevent environmental degradation but also to secure the long-term sustainability of the battery industry itself (9, 11, 12). The EOL battery challenge is characterized by a critical duality. On one hand, spent LIBs are classified as hazardous waste, containing a complex amalgam of reactive, flammable, and toxic components that pose significant risks to both human health and ecological systems if managed improperly (13, 14). The potential for thermal runaway events, fires, and the leaching of heavy metals and corrosive compounds into the environment necessitates stringent regulatory oversight and sophisticated management protocols (15–17). On the other hand, these same EOL batteries represent a rich and concentrated secondary resource of valuable and, in many cases, critical raw materials. They contain significant quantities of cobalt, nickel, manganese, lithium, copper, and aluminium – materials whose primary extraction is often associated with substantial environmental burdens, geopolitical supply risks, and high economic costs (3, 12, 18, 19). This duality frames the central imperative for the battery industry: to transition from a linear ‘take-make-dispose’ economic model to a circular one, wherein EOL batteries are no longer viewed as waste but as a vital feedstock for future battery production (20). This paradigm shift, embodied in ambitious legislative frameworks such as the European Union’s Battery Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 (7), is essential for transforming a potential environmental liability into a strategic economic and environmental opportunity. While this transition is a cornerstone of global carbon neutrality goals, the rapid expansion of LIB production and use introduces significant environmental impacts and intensifies resource supply risks (21). Ensuring the long-term sustainability of the energy transition thus necessitates a shift toward advanced recovery methods that can mitigate these pressures by securing secondary raw material streams (21, 22).

While public and research attention has largely focused on the recovery of valuable metals from the cathode and anode, a more insidious and complex challenge resides within a frequently overlooked component: the electrolyte (14, 23, 24). A typical LIB electrolyte consists of a lithium salt, most commonly lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6), dissolved in a mixture of flammable organic carbonate solvents, such as ethylene carbonate (EC) and dimethyl carbonate (DMC) (25). Although the electrolyte constitutes a small fraction of the total battery mass (25), it is a primary driver of risk and inefficiency throughout the EOL management chain (9). The organic solvents are highly volatile and flammable, creating a persistent risk of fire and explosion during dismantling and mechanical processing (24, 26). Furthermore, the LiPF_6 salt is thermally unstable and reacts with moisture to produce highly toxic and corrosive hydrogen fluoride (HF) gas, which poses severe occupational safety risks and damages equipment (24, 27). Beyond these hazards, destroying the electrolyte means squandering valuable resources, as its high-purity components are products of energy-intensive synthesis (24, 28).

For these reasons, the management of the electrolyte is a pillar for the entire recycling value chain. Its effective removal as a pre-treatment step is crucial not only for de-risking all subsequent operations but also for improving the quality of the final ‘black mass’ (the mixture of powdered electrolyte active materials) (29–31). An electrolyte-free black mass is a superior feedstock for downstream metallurgy, leading to higher recovery efficiencies for valuable metals (32). Therefore, the choice of electrolyte treatment technology has cascading effects on the safety, efficiency, and profitability of the entire recycling ecosystem and is a critical bottleneck to unlocking a truly circular battery economy (29, 33).

The EOL management strategies for spent LIB electrolyte span a wide spectrum of technologies, which can be classified according to their fundamental objective and their alignment with the principles of the waste management hierarchy (34). These pathways range from complete destruction, focused solely on hazard mitigation, to advanced separation techniques aimed at high-value, closed-loop material recovery (35). At the lowest tier of the management hierarchy are disposal-oriented pathways designed to eliminate the hazardous properties of the electrolyte. Incineration is a prominent example, employing high-temperature thermal decomposition (typically between 1100–1500 °C) in an oxygen-rich environment to completely break down the organic solvents and convert the inorganic salt into a more stable, albeit valueless, solid residue (9, 34, 36). While effective in destroying hazardous organic compounds, this approach is fraught with severe environmental drawbacks (35). It is characterized by extremely high energy consumption, the generation of toxic gaseous pollutants such as HF and phosphorus pentafluoride (PF_5) that necessitate

extensive and costly off-gas treatment systems, and the complete and irreversible loss of all material value. The final outputs are hazardous solid waste destined for landfill and greenhouse gas emissions (35).

An alternative disposal route is chemical neutralization (23). This wet chemical process utilizes reagents, such as sodium hydroxide (NaOH) and hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), to neutralize the acidic components resulting from $LiPF_6$ hydrolysis and to oxidize the organic solvents (37). Its primary advantage over incineration is its operation at ambient temperatures, leading to significantly lower energy consumption (36). However, it shares the same fundamental flaw: a focus on destruction rather than recovery. This pathway consumes substantial quantities of chemical reagents, generates large volumes of contaminated wastewater that require intensive treatment before discharge, and results in the total loss of the valuable organic solvents and lithium salt (38, 39). The primary objective of these disposal methods is to render hazardous material inert; a philosophy focused on problem elimination rather than resource recovery. This approach stands in stark philosophical and practical contrast to the principles of a true circular economy, which treat EOL products as resources to be perpetually retained within the economic system to preserve their value.

Moving up the hierarchy, recovery-oriented pathways aim to derive value from the spent electrolyte. However, the term 'recycling' is often applied ambiguously, encompassing processes with vastly different environmental outcomes. One such approach is vacuum pyrolysis, a thermal treatment process conducted in an inert atmosphere (40). This technology converts the electrolyte into lower-value products, namely pyrolytic gas and oil, which can be utilized for energy recovery as a substitute for fossil fuels (40, 41). While this represents a step above pure disposal by creating a product with energy value, it is more accurately defined as downcycling. This process irreversibly transforms highly ordered, high-value chemical compounds into a low-value, lower-ordered energy commodity. The environmental credit gained from substituting fossil fuels is often insufficient to offset the energy-intensive nature of the pyrolysis process itself (42, 43).

Indeed, as the present study will demonstrate, this form of 'recycling' can result in a greater climate change impact than some disposal methods due to its process footprint. At the apex of the management hierarchy are pathways designed for high-value material recovery, which embody the principles of closed-loop recycling. Distillation extraction is a prime example of such an advanced separation technology (44). This process typically involves using an aqueous solution to first extract the electrolyte from the battery components, followed by fractional distillation to selectively separate the volatile organic solvents (EC, DMC) from the non-volatile lithium salts based on differences in their boiling points (36, 45). The defining advantage of this approach is the non-destructive recovery of the electrolyte's constituent components in a high-purity state, with reported solvent recovery efficiencies exceeding 95%. These recovered materials are theoretically suitable for direct reuse in the manufacturing of new LIBs, thus closing the material loop (36). This pathway avoids the significant environmental burdens associated with the primary production of virgin solvents and lithium compounds, potentially leading to a net environmental benefit.

While the technical principles of these disparate EOL pathways are described in the scientific literature, a significant analytical void exists regarding their comparative environmental performance (46). Most existing research tends to focus on the technical feasibility, process optimization, or economic viability of a single technology in isolation (39). The scientific consensus generally indicates that pyrometallurgical processes have higher environmental impacts due to high energy consumption and toxic emissions, whereas hydrometallurgical processes have a lower overall impact but are burdened by large water and chemical consumption (46, 47). Several comparative life cycle assessment (LCA) studies have concluded that hydrometallurgical and solvent-based procedures can exhibit a lower environmental footprint, particularly in terms of global warming potential, compared to pyrometallurgical routes. Emerging technologies like direct recycling promise even lower impacts but are at a lower level of technological readiness (39, 48, 49).

Despite these general comparisons, there is a marked scarcity of studies that apply a standardized, rigorous, and holistic methodology like LCA to compare these fundamentally different strategies – disposal, downcycling, and closed-loop recycling – on a level playing field, specifically for the electrolyte component. It is particularly problematic that electrolyte recovery is often overlooked in LCA studies, even though its safe removal is crucial for minimizing the environmental impact of recycling processes (48, 50, 51). By focusing specifically on the organic electrolyte, this study supplements existing research that typically aggregates battery components, often diluting the specific environmental hotspots associated with hazardous solvent management. This focused 'gate-to-gate' approach allows for a high-resolution evaluation of how different treatment philosophies – ranging from thermal destruction to high-purity recovery – influence

the overall sustainability of the battery circular economy. This lack of comparative data creates a critical knowledge gap that is exacerbated by the ambiguous use of the term ‘recycling.’ Without robust, quantitative evidence, there is a significant risk of suboptimal policy and investment decisions. For instance, a technology labeled as ‘recycling,’ such as vacuum pyrolysis (41), might be perceived as inherently superior to a disposal method, even though its process footprint could potentially outweigh the environmental benefits of the recovered low-value product. This ambiguity hinders the development of effective, evidence-based regulations, creating a critical need for a data-driven framework that moves beyond simplistic labels to evaluate technologies based on the quality and functionality of the materials they recover (52). This necessity for data-driven frameworks is further underscored by recent perspectives calling for more robust and standardized sustainability metrics that can accurately capture the true environmental performance of various battery end-of-life pathways (22, 53). Moving beyond simplistic ‘recycling’ labels is essential for ensuring that policy incentives align with actual material circularity and long-term decarbonization goals.

The primary objective of this study is to address the identified research gap by conducting a comparative ‘gate-to-gate’ LCA of four distinct EOL management pathways for spent LIB electrolyte. The analysis evaluates two direct disposal methods (incineration and chemical neutralization) and two recycling technologies (vacuum pyrolysis and distillation extraction) to quantify and compare their potential environmental impacts across a comprehensive suite of indicators. This research makes several key contributions to the field. First, it provides, to our knowledge, the first direct quantitative comparison of these four specific pathways using a standardized LCA framework and the comprehensive Environmental Footprint 3.1 impact assessment methodology. Second, by doing so, it establishes a clear and unambiguous environmental performance hierarchy, providing robust evidence that high-quality, closed-loop material recovery is fundamentally superior to both downcycling for energy recovery and direct disposal. Finally, this study offers critical, quantitative data to support a more nuanced understanding of ‘recycling.’ It empirically demonstrates that the quality, purity, and functionality of recovered products are the primary determinants of a pathway’s overall sustainability. This evidence is vital for informing future industrial investment and for the development of intelligent environmental policies, such as the EU Battery Regulation 2023/1542 (7), that can effectively incentivize technologies capable of delivering a truly circular battery economy.

2. Methodology

The environmental impacts associated with four different pathways for managing spent LiPF_6 salt-based electrolyte from LIBs were evaluated using a LCA methodology. The analysis was conducted in accordance with general LCA principles, encompassing goal and scope definition, life cycle inventory (LCI) analysis, and life cycle impact assessment (LCIA).

2.1. Goal and scope definition

The primary goal of this study was to conduct a comparative ‘gate-to-gate’ LCA of two direct disposal methods and two recycling methods for spent LIB electrolyte. The analysis aims to quantify and compare the potential environmental impacts of these scenarios to identify the most environmentally favorable approach. The functional unit (FU) for this assessment was defined as the treatment of 100 litres of spent LIB electrolyte. The composition of the model electrolyte was based on typical formulations reported in the literature (14). The precise composition and mass balance for the FU are detailed in Table 1.

The FU of 100 litres was established to provide a standardized baseline that ensures high mathematical precision and facilitates linear scaling to industrial-scale processing plants. This volume serves as a

Table 1. Composition and mass balance of the lithium-ion battery electrolyte (14) as the functional unit of 100 litres for conducted life cycle analysis model.

Component	Weight %	Details	Mass (kg)
Ethylene carbonate (EC)	49%	density: 1.32 g/mL	66.0
Dimethyl carbonate (DMC)	40%	density: 1.07 g/ml	53.5
Lithium hexafluorophosphate (LiPF_6)	11%	concentration: 1 mol/L, molecular weight: 151.9 g/mol	15.1
Total	100%		134.6

representative intermediate scale, as it corresponds to the electrolyte volume typically recovered from approximately 2 to 3 average passenger electric vehicle battery packs (assuming an electrolyte content of 35–50 litres per vehicle depending on chemistry and capacity) (54, 55). Selecting this FU allows for a high-resolution inventory analysis while remaining grounded in the practical requirements of early-stage industrial recycling infrastructure.

The system boundaries were defined as ‘gate-to-gate’ (56). The assessment begins with the collection of the spent electrolyte (the ‘gate-in’) and ends with the final output of each process (the ‘gate-out’) as illustrated in Figure 1. For disposal scenarios, this includes final emissions and waste destined for landfill or further treatment. For recycling scenarios, this includes the recovered secondary products ready for subsequent use. This partial LCA focuses specifically on the impacts of the treatment processes themselves and intentionally excludes upstream impacts (e.g. raw material extraction for battery manufacturing) and downstream impacts related to the use phase of the recovered materials. The modeling was performed using a cut-off approach, meaning that environmental burdens are not allocated to materials that are recycled or reused outside the system boundaries.

2.2. Scenario descriptions

To assess a representative spectrum of EOL management strategies, this study evaluates four distinct scenarios for spent electrolyte treatment. These scenarios are grouped into two main categories: direct disposal and material recycling. The disposal pathways, which focus on the destruction of the electrolyte, include incineration (36, 44) and chemical neutralization (23). The recycling pathways, aimed at recovering valuable components for secondary use, include vacuum pyrolysis (41) and distillation extraction (44).

It is important to note that the process models for each scenario were developed from an analysis of available literature, primarily reflecting laboratory – or bench-scale data. Consequently, this assessment is intended to serve as an illustrative comparison of the technologies rather than a model of a specific industrial-scale operation. While these inventory data are derived from laboratory and bench-scale experiments, they represent the current state of technical feasibility and provide a high-resolution ‘theoretical potential’ for each pathway. Utilizing these data as a primary baseline is essential for a comparative assessment, as it allows for the identification of fundamental environmental hotspots and performance limits before the

Figure 1. System boundaries of the investigated life cycle assessment (LCA) process of lithium-ion battery electrolyte treatment. Procedure is defined as ‘gate-to-gate’.

complexities of industrial scaling are introduced. A comprehensive comparison of the key principles, operational parameters, and characteristics of these four methods is presented in [Table 2](#).

2.3. Life cycle inventory (LCI)

For each of the four scenarios, a detailed LCI was compiled, quantifying all material inputs (reagents, catalysts), energy consumption (electricity), and outputs (recovered products, waste streams, and emissions) relative to the FU. The primary data for process energy and material flows were derived from the literature sources referenced in [Table 1](#). The LCI data were modeled using SimaPro software (v.9.5.0.0), with background data for electricity, chemicals, transport, and waste treatment processes sourced from the Ecoinvent 3.9 database. The recycling machinery was powered by the current Czech energy mix, which consists of 50.78% fossil fuels, 42.82% nuclear energy, and 6.4% renewables ([57](#)). A detailed summary of the aggregated LCI data for each scenario, including total electricity consumption, key material inputs, and primary outputs, is provided in [Table 3](#).

The complete list of specific Ecoinvent processes used to model the background system is presented in [Table 4](#).

Furthermore, detailed process flow diagrams, which visualize the contribution of each inventory flow to the final climate change impact for all four scenarios, are available in the Appendix (Figures A1-A4).

2.4. Life cycle impact assessment (LCIA)

The potential environmental impacts were calculated using the Environmental Footprint 3.1 (EF 3.1) methodology as implemented in SimaPro. While the full analysis generated results for 27 distinct impact categories, three key categories were selected for detailed presentation and discussion due to their high relevance to industrial processes and current environmental challenges ([58](#)):

- **Climate Change:** This category assesses the global warming potential over a 100-year timeframe (GWP100), based on the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) model. It is a critical indicator of global environmental impact, quantifying greenhouse gas emissions in kg CO₂ eq.
- **Freshwater, Eutrophication:** This category measures the enrichment of freshwater ecosystems with nutrients, particularly phosphorus, which can lead to algal blooms, oxygen depletion, and biodiversity loss. It is relevant due to the potential release of phosphorus (P)-containing compounds.
- **Resource Use, Minerals and Metals:** This indicator evaluates the depletion of abiotic resources, measured in kg Antimony (Sb) eq. It is highly relevant to battery recycling, as a key goal is to reduce the demand for virgin mineral and metal resources.

3. Results

A comprehensive LCIA was performed, quantifying the performance of each of the four scenarios across a full suite of 27 environmental impact categories. While the complete dataset is provided in the Supplementary Materials (Sheets S1-S4), the primary analysis herein focuses on three key indicators: climate change, freshwater eutrophication, and resource use (minerals and metals). [Figure 2](#) presents a comparative summary of these findings, revealing significant differences between the direct disposal and recycling pathways.

3.1. Climate change

In the climate change category, the direct disposal scenarios showed the highest global warming potential (GWP). Incineration exhibited the most significant environmental burden, contributing 11.29 kg CO₂ eq. The vacuum pyrolysis recycling method also resulted in a notable positive impact of 4.56 kg CO₂ eq., followed by chemical neutralization at 2.79 kg CO₂ eq. In stark contrast, the distillation extraction method was the only scenario to achieve a negative result, yielding an environmental credit of -2.46 kg CO₂ eq. This negative

Table 2. A comparative summary of the key process parameters and characteristics for the four assessed electrolyte treatment and disposal methods.

Process Type Parameter	Direct disposal		Recycling	
	Incineration	Chemical Neutralization	Vacuum Pyrolysis	Distillation Extraction
Principle	High-temperature thermal decomposition of organic and inorganic compounds in an oxygen-rich environment.	Neutralization of acidic components (from LiPF ₆ hydrolysis) via an acid-base reaction, followed by oxidation of organic solvents.	Catalytic thermal decomposition of the electrolyte in an inert atmosphere under vacuum to produce valuable fuels.	Selective separation of volatile organic solvents from non-volatile salts via fractional distillation, preceded by aqueous extraction.
Key Process Steps	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Preparation: Input analysis of electrolyte; preheating of the combustion chamber and filtration systems. Combustion: Injection of electrolyte into a furnace at 1100–1500°C for thermal decomposition. Gas Treatment: Multi-stage filtration and neutralization of acid gases (e.g. HF) with NaOH. Waste Handling: Collection and disposal of solid residues from filters as hazardous waste. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Preparation: Dosing of neutralizing (e.g. NaOH) and oxidizing (e.g. H₂O₂) agents into a corrosion-resistant reaction vessel. Neutralization: Controlled addition of the electrolyte to the vessel; the exothermic reaction is monitored. Separation: Filtration and sedimentation to remove solid precipitates (e.g. NaF). Wastewater Treatment: Final processing of the resulting aqueous solution before discharge. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Catalyst Preparation: Synthesis and activation of a CaO-ZSM-5 catalyst. Pyrolysis: The electrolyte is mixed with the catalyst, placed in a vacuum tube furnace, and heated to 530°C under vacuum (100 Pa). Product Collection: The resulting pyrolytic gases and oils are condensed and collected for secondary use. Residue Handling: Processing of the solid residue. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Extraction: An Aqueous Extracting and Extracting Solution (AEES) is used to separate the electrolyte from electrode materials. Solid Separation: Solid electrode materials are filtered from the electrolyte-containing solution. Distillation: The solution is heated to 242–248 °C in a rotary evaporator to distill the volatile organic solvents (EC, DMC). Product Recovery: The purified organic solvents are condensed, and the remaining salt sediments are recovered via filtration.
Primary Outputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gaseous emissions (CO₂, H₂O). Hazardous solid waste containing NaF. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A neutralized aqueous solution requiring wastewater treatment. Solid precipitates. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pyrolytic gas and oil (light fuel). Solid residue containing CaF₂. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High purity recovered organic solvents (EC, DMC). Sediments of reusable salts (NaPF₆, Li₂CO₃).
Stated Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simple process flow. Suitable for various LIB chemistries. Capable of high-throughput processing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Low energy consumption compared to thermal methods. Operates at ambient temperature. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Converts waste into energy products (pyrolytic fuel). High conversion efficiency (up to 91.47% to light fuel reported). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High recovery efficiency of organic solvents (>95%). Recovers materials for direct reuse, supporting a circular economy. Non-destructive recovery of components.
Stated Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High energy consumption. Produces toxic gaseous pollutants (HF, PF₅) requiring extensive off-gas treatment. No material recovery. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generates a significant volume of wastewater. Consumes chemical reagents. Risk of incomplete reaction or formation of secondary pollutants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Requires high initial investment for specialized equipment. Energy-intensive process. Catalyst preparation adds complexity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential for thermal decomposition of LiPF₆ if not precisely controlled. Requires management of the AEES.
Reference	(36, 44)	(23, 36, 37)	(36, 41)	(36, 44)

Figure 2. Comparative environmental impacts of the four scenarios of electrolyte treatment (direct disposal: incineration, chemical neutralization; recycling: vacuum pyrolysis, distillation extraction) scenarios for the selected categories: climate change, freshwater eutrophication, and resource use, minerals and metals). The results correspond to the functional unit of treating 100 litres of spent electrolyte.

value indicates that the recovery and reuse of materials from this process avoids more greenhouse gas emissions than the process itself generates.

3.2. Freshwater eutrophication

A similar trend was observed for freshwater eutrophication, which measures the potential for nutrient enrichment in water bodies. Incineration again demonstrated the highest impact, with a value of 14.1×10^{-3} kg P eq. Vacuum pyrolysis and chemical neutralization followed with smaller, yet still detrimental, impacts of 3.14×10^{-3} kg P eq. and 1.98×10^{-3} kg P eq., respectively. Consistent with the climate change results, distillation extraction was the only method to show a net environmental benefit, with an impact of -0.51×10^{-3} kg P eq.

3.3. Resource use, minerals and metals

Regarding the depletion of abiotic resources, the results followed the established pattern. Incineration had the highest impact on mineral and metal resources, measured at 6.38×10^{-5} kg Sb eq., followed by vacuum pyrolysis with an impact of 4.65×10^{-5} kg Sb eq. Chemical neutralization showed the lowest positive impact among the first three methods at 1.72×10^{-5} kg Sb eq. Once again, the distillation extraction process resulted in a significant environmental credit of -4.98×10^{-5} kg Sb eq., indicating that the value of the recovered materials outweighs the resources consumed during the recycling process. In summary, across all three highlighted environmental categories, the direct disposal methods consistently resulted in the highest environmental burdens. Of the recycling methods, distillation extraction was uniquely identified as providing a net environmental benefit, while vacuum pyrolysis still carried a significant environmental impact, comparable to or greater than chemical neutralization in two of the three categories.

4. Discussion

The results of this LCA reveal a distinct environmental performance hierarchy among the evaluated EOL pathways for electrolytes from LIBs, driven primarily by the quality and functionality of the recovered

Table 3. A summary of the key life cycle inventory (LCI) data used for modeling the four electrolyte treatment scenarios.

Process Type Inventory Parameter	Direct disposal		Recycling	
	Incineration	Chemical Neutralization	Vacuum Pyrolysis	Distillation Extraction
Energy Inputs				
Energy Consumption of Key Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lab. Equipment (Chromatographs, Spectrometers): 5 kWh. Ventilation System: 15 kWh (3 h operation). Filtration Systems: System 1: 12 kWh (3 h operation). System 2: 4 kWh (2 h operation). System 3: 10 kWh (5 h operation). High-Temperature Furnace: 1200 kWh (4 h operation). Monitoring: 20 kWh (2 h operation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mixing System: 16 kWh (2 h operation). Ventilation System: 30 kWh (3 h operation). Use of Neutralizing Agents (Mixing & Control): 4 kWh (0.5 h operation). Filtration Systems: System 1: 8 kWh (2 h operation). System 2: 6 kWh (1 h operation). Sodification and Waste Preparation: 3 kWh. Water Purification: 2 kWh. Monitoring: System 1: 40 kWh (2 h operation). System 2: 8 kWh (1 h operation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mixing System: 2 kWh (1 h operation). Vacuum Furnace: 36 kWh (12 h operation). Vacuum Tube Furnaces: System 1: 20 kWh (4 h operation). System 2: 80 kWh. Monitoring: 20 kWh (2 h operation). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mixing Systems: 1 kWh (1 h operation). Rotating Sieve Systems: 1 kWh (1 h operation). Temperature Regulation Systems: 1 kWh (1 h operation). Filtration Systems: 2 kWh (1 h operation). Drying Systems: 10 kWh (5 h operation). Distillation Systems: 25 kWh. Monitoring: 20 kWh (2 h operation).
Total Electricity	1266 kWh	117 kWh	158 kWh	60 kWh
Key Material Inputs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sodium hydroxide (NaOH): 45 kg Oxygen (O₂): 10 kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sodium hydroxide (NaOH): 75 kg Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂): 20 kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zeolite (ZSM-5): 80.8 kg Quicklime (CaO): 53.8 kg Deionized water: 20 kg Nitrogen (N₂): 10 kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> AEES solution (700 L), containing: NaOH, Na₂CO₃, and NaCl Deionized water: 200 L
Primary Outputs Recovered Products	None	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pyrolytic gas (fuel): 100 kg Pyrolytic oil (fuel): 60 kg Solid residue (for ceramics): 100 kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organic solvents (EC, DMC): 114.3 kg Salt sediments (for synthesis): 15.1 kg
Waste Streams & Emissions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hazardous solid waste (NaF, organic sludge): 70 kg Direct emissions to air (CO₂, H₂O): 50 kg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hazardous solid waste (NaF, organic sludge): 35 kg Wastewater for treatment: 90 L 	None specified (outputs are secondary products)	None specified (outputs are secondary products)
Notes System Boundary	All outputs are treated as waste, incurring an additional environmental burden for disposal.	Outputs are managed as waste and wastewater, requiring further treatment processes.	All primary outputs are modeled as valuable secondary products that substitute virgin materials.	All primary outputs are modeled as high-value secondary products, creating an environmental credit.
Model	-	-	Syngas replaces pyrolysis gas. Similarly, the pyrolysis residue is replaced by conventional petroleum oil due to its similar application.	In the modeling of AEES, sodium carbonate (Na ₂ CO ₃) was replaced by sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO ₃). In the sediments, NaPF ₆ is replaced by sodium tripolyphosphate (Na ₅ P ₃ O ₁₀).
Reference	(36, 44)	(23, 36, 37)	(36, 41)	(36, 44)

products. The most significant finding is the unique profile of distillation extraction, which emerged as the only scenario to yield a net environmental benefit across all key impact categories. This favorable outcome is attributable to the principle of 'avoided burden,' a cornerstone of LCA for recycling processes. By recovering high-purity organic solvents (EC, DMC) and lithium salts that can directly substitute virgin materials, the process generates substantial environmental credits that outweigh its own operational impacts. This

Table 4. Ecoinvent 3.9 background processes used for the LCA modeling.

Technology Scenario	Ecoinvent process	
Direct Disposal: Electrolyte Incineration	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for oxygen, liquid Cut-off, U	
	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	
	Transport, freight, light commercial vehicle {Europe without Switzerland} transport, freight, light commercial vehicle Cut-off, U	
	Electricity, low voltage {CZ} market for electricity, low voltage Cut-off, U	
	Carbon dioxide, fossil – direct emission	
	Water – direct emission	
	Sewage sludge, 70% water, WWT, WW, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of sewage sludge, 70% water, WWT, WW, average, municipal incineration Cut-off, U	
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration Cut-off, U	
	Hydrogen peroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RER} hydrogen peroxide production, product in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	
	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	
Direct Disposal: Chemical Neutralization	Transport, freight, light commercial vehicle {Europe without Switzerland} transport, freight, light commercial vehicle Cut-off, U	
	Electricity, low voltage {CZ} market for electricity, low voltage Cut-off, U	
	Sewage sludge, 70% water, WWT, WW, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of sewage sludge, 70% water, WWT, WW, average, municipal incineration Cut-off, U	
	Hazardous waste, for incineration {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of hazardous waste, hazardous waste incineration Cut-off, U	
	Wastewater, average {Europe without Switzerland} treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment Cut-off, U	
	Recycling: Vacuum Pyrolysis	Synthetic gas {RoW} synthetic gas production, from wood, at fluidized bed gasifier Cut-off, U
		Base oil {Europe without Switzerland} base oil production, petroleum refinery operation Cut-off, U
		Fluorspar, 97% purity {GLO} market for fluorspar, 97% purity Cut-off, U
		Zeolite, powder {RER} zeolite production, powder Cut-off, U
		Quicklime, milled, loose {RoW} quicklime production, milled, loose Cut-off, U
Water, deionized {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionized Cut-off, U		
Nitrogen, liquid {RER} market for nitrogen, liquid Cut-off, U		
Transport, freight, light commercial vehicle {Europe without Switzerland} transport, freight, light commercial vehicle Cut-off, U		
Electricity, low voltage {CZ} market for electricity, low voltage Cut-off, U		
Water, deionized {Europe without Switzerland} market for water, deionized Cut-off, U		
Recycling: Distillation Extraction	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {GLO} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	
	Sodium bicarbonate {RER} soda production, solvay process Cut-off, U	
	Sodium chloride, powder {RER} sodium chloride production, powder Cut-off, U	
	Ethylene carbonate {RoW} ethylene carbonate production Cut-off, U	
	Dimethyl carbonate {RER} dimethyl carbonate production Cut-off, U	
	Sodium tripolyphosphate {RER} sodium tripolyphosphate production Cut-off, U	
	Lithium carbonate {RoW} lithium carbonate production, from spodumene Cut-off, U	
	Transport, freight, light commercial vehicle {Europe without Switzerland} transport, freight, light commercial vehicle Cut-off, U	
	Electricity, low voltage {CZ} market for electricity, low voltage Cut-off, U	

Note: Geographical codes used in the process names are as follows: RER = Rest of Europe; RoW = Rest of the World; GLO = Global; CZ = Czech Republic.

outcome strongly suggests that recycling pathways designed for direct, high-quality material recovery are the most effective strategy for implementing a true circular economy for LIB electrolytes.

In stark contrast, the disposal pathways and the thermal recycling method of vacuum pyrolysis result in significant net environmental burdens. The incineration scenario stands out as the least favorable option, primarily due to its extreme energy consumption required for thermal decomposition and the subsequent need for treatment of hazardous waste streams. More nuanced is the case of vacuum pyrolysis. Although technically a recycling method, its environmental footprint was comparable to or even worse than chemical neutralization in key categories. This apparent paradox is explained by the nature of its outputs; the process is a form of downcycling that converts valuable chemical compounds into lower-grade products such as pyrolytic oils and gases intended for energy recovery. While this avoids the use of some fossil fuels, the environmental credit gained is substantially lower than that from replacing energy-intensive, high-purity chemicals.

Ultimately, these findings highlight that the term ‘recycling’ is not monolithic. The evaluated scenarios align well with the established waste management hierarchy, which prioritizes material recycling over energy recovery and disposal. Distillation extraction exemplifies high-quality material recycling (a closed-loop system), while vacuum pyrolysis represents energy recovery (an open-loop system that degrades

material value). Therefore, this analysis empirically demonstrates that for LIB electrolytes, pathways focusing on the non-destructive recovery of chemical constituents are fundamentally superior from an environmental perspective to those based on thermal conversion or destruction.

4.1. Comparison with existing literature

The findings of this study, particularly the pronounced environmental advantages of solvent-based recovery over thermal treatment, are in strong alignment with the broader scientific consensus on the life cycle impacts of LIB recycling technologies. Numerous comparative LCAs have concluded that hydrometallurgical and solvent-based pathways generally exhibit a lower environmental footprint (19, 59–61), especially in terms of global warming potential and energy consumption, compared to pyrometallurgical routes (49). The high impact of incineration quantified in our analysis, driven primarily by its substantial energy demand (1266 kWh per FU), corresponds with literature values that identify energy consumption as the principal environmental hotspot for high-temperature recycling processes (62). For instance, pyrometallurgical methods often require temperatures exceeding 1400 °C (9), which inevitably leads to significant energy inputs and associated greenhouse gas emissions, thus reinforcing our conclusion that thermal destruction is an inherently impactful EOL option (63). Our results validate the findings of Rajaeifar et al. (49) and Arshad et al. (50), who noted that while thermal treatment methods are effective for initial hazard mitigation, they fail to capture the material value of organic components, leading to significantly higher global warming potential compared to solvent-based recovery. Furthermore, our findings supplement the work of Zhang et al. (28), providing quantitative evidence that the non-destructive recovery of LiPF₆ and carbonate solvents is a decisive factor in achieving a net-positive environmental credit. This underscores that for electrolytes, the ‘avoided burden’ from high-quality material substitution is the primary driver of environmental superiority, consistent with the broader consensus on high-value battery recycling (19, 59).

Furthermore, our analysis of vacuum pyrolysis as a form of downcycling with limited environmental benefits resonates with established LCA principles on the importance of recovery quality. The magnitude of the environmental credit from recycling is directly proportional to the environmental burden of the virgin material being substituted. Our results empirically demonstrate this principle: the substitution of lower-value pyrolytic fuels generates a relatively small environmental credit, insufficient to offset the process’s own energy demand. This distinction between high-quality, closed-loop material recovery and lower-quality, open-loop energy recovery is critical and highlights that the choice of recycling pathway has profound implications for the actual circularity and sustainability of the battery value chain.

4.2. Broader implications for industry and policy

The results of this study have significant implications for industrial strategy and environmental policy. The quantitative evidence demonstrating the severe environmental burden of incineration provides a strong rationale for policymakers to steer the industry away from thermal destruction. Ambitious legislative frameworks, such as the European Union’s Battery Regulation (EU) 2023/1542 (7), mandate high material recovery targets. Our findings unequivocally show that disposal methods like incineration, which typically result in a total loss of valuable materials, are fundamentally incompatible with these circular economy objectives. Consequently, investment must be directed towards high-efficiency, closed-loop technologies like distillation extraction. For industry, however, this presents a challenge: while environmentally optimal, the technological maturity, scalability, and economic viability of such advanced solvent-based processes require further validation to bridge the gap from laboratory-scale potential to industrial-scale reality. The transition of distillation extraction from bench-scale to industrial reality involves distinct scaling factors. Large-scale implementation offers significant opportunities for improved energy efficiency through advanced heat integration and continuous flow processing, which typically reduces the energy intensity per unit compared to batch-scale laboratory equipment. However, industrial operations must also account for auxiliary energy demands from automated logistics, comprehensive safety monitoring, and large-scale emission control systems. Despite these additional burdens, the high-purity recovery of organic solvents remains a decisive driver of industrial viability, as the environmental credits gained from avoiding virgin chemical production are expected to remain the dominant factor in the overall sustainability profile.

Beyond direct electrolyte management, the findings imply broader benefits for the entire battery recycling value chain. The electrolyte, containing the reactive and thermally unstable LiPF_6 salt, is a primary source of safety risks during recycling, particularly the formation of highly toxic HF gas. Implementing an effective pre-treatment step, such as distillation extraction, to remove and stabilize the electrolyte before mechanical processing can significantly de-risk subsequent operations, enhancing worker safety and process stability. Furthermore, a clean separation of the electrolyte and organic binder components can yield a higher purity black mass. This improved feedstock quality can subsequently increase the efficiency and economic viability of the downstream metallurgical processes used to recover critical metals, thereby enhancing the performance of the entire recycling ecosystem.

4.3. Methodological limitations and scope

While this study provides a valuable comparison of EOL pathways, its conclusions must be interpreted within the context of certain methodological limitations. The primary limitation is that the LCIs were constructed based on data from laboratory- or bench-scale experiments. A significant ‘scalability gap’ often exists between laboratory results and industrial operations, where factors such as higher energy requirements for large-scale equipment, material losses, and the burden of additional infrastructure are more pronounced. Consequently, while the relative ranking of the technologies is expected to be robust, the absolute environmental impact values could change with industrial implementation. The transition from laboratory-scale data to industrial reality involves complex scaling factors that can bi-directionally influence environmental outcomes. On one hand, large-scale industrial operations typically benefit from economies of scale, particularly through advanced heat integration and continuous flow processing, which can significantly reduce energy intensity per unit compared to batch-scale laboratory equipment. On the other hand, industrial implementation introduces auxiliary energy burdens from automated logistics, comprehensive safety monitoring, and large-scale emission control systems that are often absent or simplified in laboratory settings. Despite these uncertainties, utilizing high-resolution laboratory data as a primary baseline is essential for identifying fundamental environmental hotspots and performance limits of each technology before these industrial complexities are introduced. Furthermore, given that the observed environmental performance gaps between the disposal and recycling scenarios span several orders of magnitude, the inherent ‘scalability gap’ is considered insufficient to alter the fundamental hierarchy of the evaluated pathways.

Secondly, the modeling necessitated the use of proxy processes from the Ecoinvent database to represent specific material flows for which elementary processes were unavailable. Key substitutions, as noted in the LCI, included modeling the recovered pyrolytic gas as synthetic gas and pyrolytic oil as base oil. For the distillation extraction scenario, sodium carbonate (Na_2CO_3) in the AEES solution was represented by sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3), and the recovered salt sediments (containing NaPF_6) were modeled using the sodium tripolyphosphate process. While these proxies were selected for their chemical and functional similarity, this approach inherently introduces a degree of uncertainty. The life cycle inventories for the proxy substances may differ from those of the actual compounds, which could influence the absolute magnitude of the final impact scores. To further clarify the implications of the selected proxy processes, such as modeling sodium bicarbonate for sodium carbonate or synthetic gas for pyrolytic gas, a qualitative assessment of their impact magnitude was considered. Given that the observed environmental performance gaps between the disposal and recycling scenarios span several orders of magnitude, the inherent uncertainties introduced by these material substitutions are considered insufficient to alter the fundamental hierarchy or the principal conclusions of this study. The ‘avoided burden’ credit from high-quality recovery remains the primary driver of the results, regardless of minor variances in proxy inventory data.

However, given the significant performance differences observed, this limitation is not expected to alter the fundamental ranking or the principal conclusions of this study. Finally, the findings are specific to the defined ‘gate-to-gate’ system boundaries, the ‘cut-off’ allocation method, and the regional context of the Czech electricity mix. The application of a different allocation principle or a change in the geographical context could alter the final numerical scores, although it is unlikely to change the fundamental conclusion regarding the superiority of high-quality material recovery. The sensitivity of our results to the regional energy mix is further validated by recent findings regarding LIB recycling pre-treatment within the Czech energy context. According to Pražanová et al. (48), a transition from the 2022 grid to the 2030 scenario –

characterized by a reduction in coal reliance to less than a third of the mix – results in significant environmental improvements, particularly in freshwater eutrophication (>20%) and climate change (17%). While a greener grid consistently improves the environmental profile of all EOL pathways, the absolute benefits remain dependent on specific facility efficiencies and material compositions. For energy-intensive processes like incineration, a cleaner grid reduces direct process emissions but cannot mitigate the total loss of material value. Conversely, for distillation extraction, the ‘avoided burden’ credit from recovered materials remains the dominant factor, suggesting that the environmental superiority of high-value recovery is maintained and potentially amplified under future decarbonized conditions. This underscores that while our established hierarchy is robust, individualized LCA remains an imperative for specific industrial applications to account for variability in technology and regional energy structures.

4.4. Future research directions

Building upon the findings and limitations of this study, several key avenues for future research can be identified. The most critical next step is to conduct a pilot-scale validation of the distillation extraction technology. Collecting real-world industrial data would allow for the development of a refined LCI, thus confirming the promising results of this study at a higher level of technological readiness. To ensure industrial relevance, this experimental validation should be conducted in parallel with a comprehensive techno-economic analysis (TEA). Integrating the environmental data from the LCA with the economic data from a TEA is essential for holistically evaluating the technology’s overall viability. Finally, further research should focus on process optimization, such as investigating the potential for recycling the AEES to minimize secondary waste streams and expanding the system boundaries to perform a full ‘cradle-to-cradle’ analysis. Such a multi-faceted research approach is crucial for translating promising laboratory results into robust, sustainable, and economically sound industrial solutions for the battery value chain.

5. Conclusion

This study conducted a comparative LCA to quantify the environmental impacts of four distinct EOL pathways for spent LIB electrolytes: two direct disposal methods (incineration, chemical neutralization) and two recycling technologies (vacuum pyrolysis, distillation extraction). The analysis revealed a stark and compelling hierarchy of environmental performance, unequivocally demonstrating that the quality and functionality of recovered materials are the primary determinants of a pathway’s sustainability. The principal conclusion of this research is that a clear distinction must be made between different forms of recycling. Pathways designed for high-quality, closed-loop material recovery, as exemplified by distillation extraction, are fundamentally superior to those focused on thermal conversion or destruction.

Our findings empirically establish that distillation extraction is the only assessed method capable of achieving a net environmental benefit. By recovering high-purity chemical constituents (EC, DMC, and lithium salts, such as LiPF₆) that can directly substitute virgin raw materials, this process generates significant environmental credits that outweigh its operational impacts, presenting a benchmark for a truly circular management strategy. In contrast, thermal destruction via incineration was identified as the most environmentally detrimental option, characterized by extreme energy consumption and the generation of secondary hazardous waste, making it incompatible with modern circular economy principles. Furthermore, the analysis highlights that thermal conversion via vacuum pyrolysis, while technically a form of recycling, represents a low-grade downcycling pathway. Its conversion of valuable chemicals into lower-value fuels provides only marginal environmental credits, insufficient to offset its own significant process footprint.

The implications of this research extend beyond a simple technological comparison. For policymakers, this study provides a quantitative rationale to design regulations, such as the EU Battery Regulation, that actively incentivize technologies promoting high-quality material circularity over mere energy recovery or disposal. For the industry, it underscores the strategic importance of investing in advanced separation and purification technologies as a cornerstone of sustainable and resilient battery value chains. While this work is based on laboratory-scale data and further pilot-scale validation is a critical next step, it provides a foundational framework for decision-making.

Ultimately, this research contributes to a more nuanced understanding of battery recycling, shifting the focus from the question if we should recycle to how we should recycle. The transition to a sustainable electric mobility ecosystem depends not only on the innovation of the batteries we build but, just as critically, on the intelligence and efficiency with which we deconstruct them. Ensuring that every component, including the often-overlooked electrolyte, is perpetually kept in circulation through optimized, high-value recovery pathways is not merely an option for waste management; it is an imperative for the future of green technology.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Zbyněk Plachý: Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing.

Michael Fridrich: Formal analysis, Data curation, Investigation, Writing – Review & Editing.

Anna Pražanová: Resources, Methodology, Conceptualization, Writing – Original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Author contributions

CRediT: **Zbyněk Plachý**: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing; **Michael Fridrich**: Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing; **Anna Pražanová**: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – original draft.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

Funding

This work was financially supported by the Czech Science Foundation, grant No. 23-07984X, and the Grant Agency of the CTU in Prague, grant No. SGS24/136/OHK3/3T/13. Additionally, the infrastructure used was made available through the project 'The Energy Conversion and Storage', funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research.Grantová agentura ČR.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Z. P., upon reasonable request.

Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author(s) used Google's Gemini 2.5 to improve text readability and organize ideas into a coherent and logical structure. The authors have reviewed and edited the output and take full responsibility for the content of this publication.

References

- [1] Wang, Y.; Yin, H.; An, L.; Wang, Y.; Yin, H.; An, L. An Upcoming Global Challenge: Efficient Recycling for End-of-Life Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Global Challenges* **2022**, *6* (12), 2200184. doi:10.1002/GCH2.202200184.
- [2] Cusenza, M.A.; Guarino, F.; Longo, S.; Ferraro, M.; Cellura, M. Energy and Environmental Benefits of Circular Economy Strategies: The Case Study of Reusing Used Batteries from Electric Vehicles. *Journal of Energy Storage* **2019**, *25*, 100845. doi:10.1016/J.EST.2019.100845.
- [3] Bonsu, N.O. Towards a Circular and Low-Carbon Economy: Insights from the Transitioning to Electric Vehicles and net Zero Economy. *J. Cleaner Prod.* **2020**, *256*, 120659. doi:10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2020.120659.
- [4] Martinez-Laserna, E.; Gandiaga, I.; Sarasketa-Zabala, E.; Badedo, J.; Stroe, D.-I.; Swierczynski, M.; Goikoetxea, A. Battery Second Life: Hype, Hope or Reality? A Critical Review of the State of the Art. *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* **2018**, *93*, 701–718. doi:10.1016/J.RSER.2018.04.035.

- [5] Miao, Y.; Hynan, P.; Von Jouanne, A.; Yokochi, A. Current Li-Ion Battery Technologies in Electric Vehicles and Opportunities for Advancements. *Energies* **2019**, *12* (6), 1074. doi:10.3390/EN12061074.
- [6] Wang, X.; Gaustad, G.; Babbitt, C.W.; Richa, K. Economies of Scale for Future Lithium-Ion Battery Recycling Infrastructure. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2014**, *83*, 53–62. doi:10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2013.11.009.
- [7] Regulation (EU). 2023/1542 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 July 2023 Concerning Batteries and Waste Batteries, Amending Directive 2008/98/EC and Regulation (EU) 2019/1020 and repealing Directive 2006/66/EC (Text with EEA relevance). <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2023/1542/oj/eng> (accessed Apr. 15, 2025).
- [8] Harper, G.; Sommerville, R.; Kendrick, E.; Driscoll, L.; Slater, P.; Stolkin, R.; Walton, A.; Christensen, P.; Heidrich, O.; Lambert, S.; Abbott, A.; Ryder, K.; Gaines, L.; Anderson, P. Recycling Lithium-Ion Batteries from Electric Vehicles. *Nature* **2019**, *575* (7781), 75–86. doi:10.1038/S41586-019-1682-5.
- [9] Pražanová, A.; Knap, V.; Stroe, D.-I. Literature Review, Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries from Electric Vehicles, Part I: Recycling Technology. *Energies* **2022**, *15* (3), 1086. doi:10.3390/EN15031086.
- [10] An, L. "Recycling of spent lithium-ion Batteries: Processing Methods and Environmental Impacts," *Recycl. Spent Lithium-Ion Batter. Process. Methods Environ. Impacts*. pp. 1–217. 2019.
- [11] Armand, M.; Axmann, P.; Bresser, D.; Copley, M.; Edström, K.; Ekberg, C.; Guyomard, D.; Lestriez, B.; Novák, P.; Petranikova, M.; Porcher, W.; Trabesinger, S.; Wohlfahrt-Mehrens, M.; Zhang, H.. Lithium-Ion Batteries – Current State of the Art and Anticipated Developments. *J. Power Sources*. **2020**, *479*, 228708. DOI: 10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2020.228708.
- [12] Pražanová, A.; Knap, V.; Stroe, D.-I. Literature Review, Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries from Electric Vehicles, Part II: Environmental and Economic Perspective. *Energies* **2022**, *15* (19), 7356. doi:10.3390/EN15197356.
- [13] Sobianowska-Turek, A.; Urbańska, W.; Janicka, A.; Zawiślak, M.; Matla, J. The Necessity of Recycling of Waste Li-Ion Batteries Used in Electric Vehicles as Objects Posing a Threat to Human Health and the Environment. *Recycling* **2021**, *6* (2), 35. doi:10.3390/RECYCLING6020035.
- [14] Zackrisson, M.; Schellenberger, S. "Toxicity of Lithium Ion Battery Chemicals-Overview with Focus on Recycling."
- [15] Ma, S.; Jiang, M.; Tao, P.; Song, C.; Wu, J.; Wang, J.; Deng, T.; Shang, W. Temperature Effect and Thermal Impact in Lithium-Ion Batteries: A Review. *Progress in Natural Science: Materials International* **2018**, *28* (6), 653–666. doi:10.1016/J.PNSC.2018.11.002.
- [16] Wang, Q.; Ping, P.; Zhao, X.; Chu, G.; Sun, J.; Chen, C. Thermal Runaway Caused Fire and Explosion of Lithium Ion Battery. *J. Power Sources* **2012**, *208*, 210–224. doi:10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2012.02.038.
- [17] Golubkov, A.W.; Fuchs, D.; Wagner, J.; Wiltzsche, H.; Stangl, C.; Fauler, G.; Voitic, G.; Thaler, A.; Hacker, V. Thermal-Runaway Experiments on Consumer Li-Ion Batteries with Metal-Oxide and Olivin-Type Cathodes. *RSC Adv.* **2014**, *4* (7), 3633–3642. doi:10.1039/C3RA45748F.
- [18] Vanitha, M.; Balasubramanian, N. Waste Minimization and Recovery of Valuable Metals from Spent Lithium-ion Batteries – a Review. *Environmental Technology Reviews* **2013**, *2* (1), 101–115.
- [19] Fan, E.; Li, L.; Wang, Z.; Lin, J.; Huang, Y.; Yao, Y.; Chen, R.; Wu, F. Sustainable Recycling Technology for Li-Ion Batteries and Beyond: Challenges and Future Prospects. *Chem. Rev.* **2020**, *120* (14), 7020–7063. doi:10.1021/ACS.CHEMREV.9B00535.
- [20] Vinayak, A.K.; Li, M.; Huang, X.; Dong, P.; Amine, K.; Lu, J.; Wang, X. Circular Economies for Lithium-Ion Batteries and Challenges to Their Implementation. *Next Materials* **2024**, *5*, 100231. doi:10.1016/J.NXMATE.2024.100231.
- [21] Chen, Q.; Lai, X.; Zhang, Y.; Chen, J.; Zhu, Z.; Huang, Y.; Zheng, Y.; Song, X.; Tang, B.; Han, X.; Lu, L.; Ouyang, M. Environmental Impacts and Supply Risks for LiFePO₄ - LiCo Ni Mn O₂ Hybrid Battery Pack in China. *Process Saf. Environ. Prot.* **2025**, *198*, 107115. doi:10.1016/J.PSEP.2025.107115.
- [22] Chen, Q.; Lai, X.; Chen, J.; Huang, Y.; Guo, Y.; Wang, Y.; Han, X.; Lu, L.; Sun, Y.; Ouyang, M.; Zheng, Y. A Critical Comparison of LCA Calculation Models for the Power Lithium-Ion Battery in Electric Vehicles During Use-Phase. *Energy* **2024**, *296*, 131175. doi:10.1016/J.ENERGY.2024.131175.
- [23] Yu, J.; Huang, K.; Zheng, J.; Zhang, L. Advance Technology for Treatment and Recycling of Electrolyte and Organic Matters from Spent Lithium-Ion Battery. *Current Opinion in Green and Sustainable Chemistry* **2024**, *47*, 100914. doi:10.1016/J.COAGSC.2024.100914.
- [24] Niu, B.; Xu, Z.; Xiao, J.; Qin, Y. Recycling Hazardous and Valuable Electrolyte in Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries: Urgency, Progress, Challenge, and Viable Approach. *Chem. Rev.* **Jul. 2023**, *123* (13), 8718–8735. doi:10.1021/ACS.CHEMREV.3C00174/ASSET/IMAGES/MEDIUM/CR3C00174_0009.GIF.
- [25] David, L.; Thomas, R.B. *Handbook of Batteries*, 4th ed. **2002**.
- [26] Ma, X.; Zhang, D.; Wen, J.; Fan, L.; Rao, A.M.; Lu, B. Sustainable Electrolytes: Design Principles and Recent Advances. *Chemistry – A European Journal* **2024**, *30* (36), e202400332. doi:10.1002/CHEM.202400332.
- [27] Mao, Z.; Song, Y.; Zhen, A.G.; Sun, W. Recycling of Electrolyte from Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Next Sustainability* **2024**, *3*, 100015. doi:10.1016/J.NXSUST.2023.100015.
- [28] Zhang, R.; Shi, X.; Esan, O.C.; An, L. Organic Electrolytes Recycling from Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Global Challenges* **2022**, *6* (12), 2200050. doi:10.1002/GCH2.202200050.
- [29] Kim, S.; Bang, J.; Yoo, J.; Shin, Y.; Bae, J.; Jeong, J.; Kim, K.; Dong, P.; Kwon, K. A Comprehensive Review on the Pretreatment Process in Lithium-Ion Battery Recycling. *J. Cleaner Prod.* **2021**, *294*, 126329. doi:10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2021.126329.

- [30] Xu, Z.; Zhiyuan, L.; Wenjun, M.; Qinxin, Z. Pretreatment Options for the Recycling of Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries: A Comprehensive Review. *Journal of Energy Storage* **2023**, *72*, 108691. doi:10.1016/J.EST.2023.108691.
- [31] Partinen, J.; Halli, P.; Varonen, A.; Wilson, B.P.; Lundström, M. Investigating Battery Black Mass Leaching Performance as a Function of Process Parameters by Combining Leaching Experiments and Regression Modeling. *Miner. Eng.* **2024**, *215*, 108828. doi:10.1016/J.MINENG.2024.108828.
- [32] Vanderbruggen, A., et al. Lithium-Ion Battery Recycling—Influence of Recycling Processes on Component Liberation and Flotation Separation Efficiency. *ACS ES T Eng.* **Nov. 2022**, *2* (11), 2130–2141. doi:10.1021/ACSESTENG.2C00177/ASSET/IMAGES/LARGE/EE2C00177_0012.JPEG.
- [33] Brückner, L.; Frank, J.; Elwert, T. Industrial Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries—A Critical Review of Metallurgical Process Routes. *Metals. (Basel)* **2020**, *10* (8), 1107–29. doi:10.3390/MET10081107.
- [34] Al-Asheh, S.; Aidan, A.; Allawi, T.; Hammoud, F.; Al Ali, H.; Khamiri, M.A. Treatment and Recycling of Spent Lithium-Based Batteries: A Review. *J. Mater. Cycles Waste Manag.* **Jan. 2024**, *26* (1), 76–95. doi:10.1007/S10163-023-01842-1/FIGURES/10.
- [35] Mroziak, W.; Rajaeifar, M.A.; Heidrich, O.; Christensen, P. Environmental Impacts, Pollution Sources and Pathways of Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2021**, *14* (12), 6099–6121. doi:10.1039/D1EE00691F.
- [36] Xu, R.; Lei, S.; Wang, T.; Yi, C.; Sun, W.; Yang, Y. Lithium Recovery and Solvent Reuse from Electrolyte of Spent Lithium-Ion Battery. *Waste Manage.* **2023**, *167*, 135–140. doi:10.1016/J.WASMAN.2023.05.034.
- [37] Zhang, Q.; Dong, T.; Li, J.; Liu, Y.; Zhang, H. Research Progress on the Recovery and High-Value Utilization of Spent Electrolyte from Lithium-Ion Batteries. *Energy Storage Sci. Technol.* **Sep. 2022**, *11* (9), 2798. doi:10.19799/J.CNKI.2095-4239.2022.0338.
- [38] Xiao, J.; Guo, J.; Zhan, L.; Xu, Z. A Cleaner Approach to the Discharge Process of Spent Lithium ion Batteries in Different Solutions. *J. Cleaner Prod.* **2020**, *255*, 120064. doi:10.1016/J.JCLEPRO.2020.120064.
- [39] Cerrillo-Gonzalez, M.d.M.; Villen-Guzman, M.; Vereda-Alonso, C.; Rodriguez-Maroto, J.M.; Paz-Garcia, J.M. Towards Sustainable Lithium-Ion Battery Recycling: Advancements in Circular Hydrometallurgy. *Processes* **2024**, *12* (7), 1485. doi:10.3390/PR12071485.
- [40] Tao, R.; Xing, P.; Li, H.; Sun, Z.; Wu, Y. Recovery of Spent LiCoO₂ Lithium-Ion Battery via Environmentally Friendly Pyrolysis and Hydrometallurgical Leaching. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2022**, *176*, 105921. doi:10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2021.105921.
- [41] Zhang, Y.; Zhang, X.; Zhu, P.; Li, W.; Zhang, L. Defluorination and Directional Conversion to Light Fuel by Lithium Synergistic Vacuum Catalytic co-Pyrolysis for Electrolyte and Polyvinylidene Fluoride in Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries. *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2023**, *460*, 132445. doi:10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2023.132445.
- [42] Jie, Y.; Yang, S.; Li, Y.; Hu, F.; Zhao, D.; Chang, D.; Lai, Y.; Chen, Y. Waste Organic Compounds Thermal Treatment and Valuable Cathode Materials Recovery from Spent LiFePO₄Batteries by Vacuum Pyrolysis. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *8* (51), 19084–19095. doi:10.1021/acssuschemeng.0c07424.
- [43] Wang, J.; Hong, D.; Zhao, D.; Cui, X.; Song, L.; Zhu, J.; Wang, Y.; Zong, F.; Zhang, N.; Li, S. A Review for High-Value Utilization of Retired Spent Electrolyte for Lithium-Ion Battery: How to Reduce the Waste of Resources? *Ionic* **2025**, *31* (7), 6635–6652. doi:10.1007/s11581-025-06355-5.
- [44] He, K.; Zhang, Z.Y.; Alai, L.; Zhang, F.S. A Green Process for Exfoliating Electrode Materials and Simultaneously Extracting Electrolyte from Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries. *J. Hazard. Mater.* **2019**, *375*, 43–51. doi:10.1016/J.JHAZMAT.2019.03.120.
- [45] Wang, Q.; Sun, J.; Chen, C. Thermal Stability of LiPF₆/EC + DMC + EMC Electrolyte for Lithium Ion Batteries. *Rare Met.* **2006**, *25* (6), 94–99. doi:10.1016/S1001-0521(07)60052-7.
- [46] Hossain, R.; Sarkar, M.; Sahajwalla, V. Technological Options and Design Evolution for Recycling Spent Lithium-Ion Batteries: Impact, Challenges, and Opportunities. *WIREs Energy and Environment* **2023**, *12* (5), e481. doi:10.1002/WENE.481.
- [47] “Environmental Impacts of Pyro – and Hydrometallurgical Recycling for Lithium-Ion Batteries – A Review – Business Chemistry.”. <https://www.businesschemistry.org/article/4899-2/> (accessed Aug. 24, 2025).
- [48] Pražanová, A.; Fridrich, M.; Weinzettel, J.; Knap, V. Gate-to-gate Life Cycle Assessment of Lithium-Ion Battery Recycling pre-Treatment. *Cleaner Environmental Systems* **2025**, *16*, 100263. doi:10.1016/J.CESYS.2025.100263.
- [49] Rajaeifar, M.A.; Raugei, M.; Steubing, B.; Hartwell, A.; Anderson, P.A.; Heidrich, O. Life Cycle Assessment of Lithium-Ion Battery Recycling Using Pyrometallurgical Technologies. *J. Ind. Ecol.* **2021**, *25* (6), 1560–1571. doi:10.1111/JIEC.13157.
- [50] Arshad, F.; Lin, J.; Manurkar, N.; Fan, E.; Ahmad, A.; Tariq, M.-u.-N.; Wu, F.; Chen, R.; Li, L. Life Cycle Assessment of Lithium-Ion Batteries: A Critical Review. *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* **2022**, *180*, 106164. doi:10.1016/J.RESCONREC.2022.106164.
- [51] Paul, D.; Pechancová, V.; Saha, N.; Pavelková, D.; Saha, N.; Motiei, M.; Jamatia, T.; Chaudhuri, M.; Ivanichenko, A.; Venher, M.; Hrbáčková, L.; Saha, P. Life Cycle Assessment of Lithium-Based Batteries: Review of Sustainability Dimensions. *Renewable Sustainable Energy Rev.* **2024**, *206*, 114860. doi:10.1016/J.RSER.2024.114860.
- [52] Gutsch, M.; Leker, J. Costs, Carbon Footprint, and Environmental Impacts of Lithium-ion Batteries – from Cathode Active Material Synthesis to Cell Manufacturing and Recycling. *Appl. Energy* **2024**, *353*, 122132. doi:10.1016/J.APENERGY.2023.122132.

- [53] Mohr, M.; Peters, J.F.; Baumann, M.; Weil, M. Toward a Cell-Chemistry Specific Life Cycle Assessment of Lithium-ion Battery Recycling Processes. *J. Ind. Ecol.* **2020**, *24* (6), 1310–1322. doi:10.1111/JIEC.13021.
- [54] Ellingsen, L.A.W.; Singh, B.; Strømman, A.H. The Size and Range Effect: Lifecycle Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Electric Vehicles. *Environ. Res. Lett.* **2016**, *11* (5), 054010. doi:10.1088/1748-9326/11/5/054010.
- [55] Spiewak, M.; Piątek, J.; Rodrigues, B.V.M.; Slabon, A. Sustainable Recycling of Lithium-Ion Batteries: Pipe Dream or Realistic Solution. *Cell Reports Sustainability* **2025**, *2* (7), 100429. doi:10.1016/j.crsus.2025.100429.
- [56] Klöpffer, W.; Grahl, B. "Life Cycle Assessment (LCA): A Guide to Best Practice," *Life Cycle Assess. A Guid. to Best Pract.*, pp. 1–396, 2014.
- [57] Czech electricity and gas market operator (OTE a.s.). "National Residual Mix, Czech Republic — English," 2024. https://www.ote-cr.cz/en/statistics/national-residual-mix?set_language=en (accessed Jul. 30, 2024).
- [58] "European Platform on LCA | EPLCA," 2024. <https://eplca.jrc.ec.europa.eu/EnvironmentalFootprint.html> (accessed Sep. 04, 2024).
- [59] Zhang, G.; Shi, M.; Hu, X.; Yang, H.; Yan, X. Comparison of Life Cycle Assessment of Different Recycling Methods for Decommissioned Lithium Iron Phosphate Batteries. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments* **2024**, *68*, 103871. doi:10.1016/J.SETA.2024.103871.
- [60] Romare, M.; Dahllöf, L. "The Life Cycle Energy Consumption and Greenhouse Gas Emissions from Lithium-Ion Batteries A Study with Focus on Current Technology and Batteries for Light-Duty Vehicles," 2017, Accessed: Jul. 20, 2024. www.ivl.se.
- [61] Arshad, F.; Li, L.; Amin, K.; Fan, E.; Manurkar, N.; Ahmad, A.; Yang, J.; Wu, F.; Chen, R. A Comprehensive Review of the Advancement in Recycling the Anode and Electrolyte from Spent Lithium Ion Batteries. *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2020**, *8* (36), 13527–13554. doi:10.1021/ACSSUSCHEMENG.0C04940.
- [62] Scrucca, F.; Presciutti, A.; Baldinelli, G.; Barberio, G.; Postriotti, L.; Karaca, C. Life Cycle Assessment of Li-Ion Batteries for Electric Vehicles: A Review Focused on the Production Phase Impact. *J. Power Sources* **2025**, *639*, 236703. doi:10.1016/J.JPOWSOUR.2025.236703.
- [63] Meshram, P.; Abhilash, A.M.; Sahu, R. Environmental Impact of Spent Lithium ion Batteries and Green Recycling Perspectives by Organic Acids – A Review. *Chemosphere* **2020**, *242*, 125291. doi:10.1016/J.CHEMOSPHERE.2019.125291.